

Implementation of project management structure

Deliverable D1.1.

Submission Date: 30 January 2019

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In the EU over 100 million tonnes of biowaste are thrown away each year. Currently 75% of this goes to landfill or is incinerated, causing major environmental problems biowaste produces greenhouse gases when it decomposes and contaminates soil and groundwater. Landfilling of biowaste goes against the principle of a circular economy and is a waste of nutrients, energy and resources for bioproducts. In this sense, SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate innovative solutions to transform urban biowaste into high value-added products, helping cities to increase their recycling rate and creating new circular economy business opportunities.

A correct project management is essential to ensure smooth collaboration and apply personalised tools for efficient implantation activities, decision making and steering; to anticipate, monitor and assess project progress vs work plan and initiating if necessary prompt corrective actions; to assure timely reporting and communication with the project officer and the EC and to perform a Risk and Quality Management strategy as well as a Data Management Plan.

This deliverable tackles the implementation of project management procedure for SCALIBUR project. The deliverable includes details on the procedures implemented for internal and external communication, composition and functions of the Decision Bodies, timing and meeting organisation, procedures regarding submitting deliverables to European Commission and implementation of the working plan.

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